

DISTRIBUTION OF SPARINGLY SOLUBLE SALTS IN PERIODIC STRUCTURES

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Six, different types of banded structures were analysed and the amount of sparingly soluble salt per g. of gel present in rings was found many times more than present in clear spaces. But in case of AgCl and AgI bands in the otherwise continued deposits the quantities present were almost the same.

Dhar and Chatterji (*Kolloid Z.*, 1922, 31, 15; 1925, 37, 2, 89; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 41) pointed out the existence of two types of Liesegang rings. In one, rings are separated by clear spaces. This type was the one described by Liesegang himself. The other type consists of continuous precipitate in which bands occur.

Analytical investigations of bands and clear spaces were first undertaken by Popp (reported by Wo. Ostwald, *Kolloid Z.*, 1925, 36, 380), Fricke and Suwelack (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1926, 124, 359) and Hedges and Henly (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2174). Results obtained by Popp and Hedges and Henly were quite contradictory. The divergence was explained on the ground that probably the determinations reported by Ostwald were on newborn rings, while that of Hedges and Henly were on completed structure after a week. It therefore appears that the problem requires further investigations. In the present work the amount of sparingly soluble salt per gram of gel in the two types has been determined.

EXPERIMENTAL

D. G. H. Eagle brand gelatin was used and it was purified by the method of Loeb (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1918, 1, 235) to give ash-free gelatin. Bacto agar-agar from Defco Laboratories was used after thoroughly washing and purifying. 5% Gelatin and 1% agar-agar gel were used. Glass tubes of uniform bore were taken into pieces of 8" in length and 5/8" in diameter, cleaned thoroughly, dried and corked at one end. Gelatin or agar-agar containing 1% of CuSO₄, ZnCl₂, AgNO₃, Pb(NO₃)₂, distributed evenly, was allowed to set in them and 30, 20 and 10% of the diffusing electrolytes were poured in the respective tubes. The rings were analysed after two weeks. The device for removing the gel from the tube was the same as that of Hedges and Henly (*loc. cit.*). In order to ascertain the interference due to the presence of gelatin or agar-agar in the estimations of sparingly soluble salts present in the gel, known quantities of PbI₂ were taken and uniformly distributed in agar-agar and gelatin and then estimated. The results are given below :

Wt. of PbSO₄ after the oxidation of gel with HNO₃ = 0.0688 g.

Wt. of PbSO₄ theoretically = 0.0682 g.

The result shows that the gel does not interfere in analysis. Hence in all the experiments the gel was oxidised with HNO_3 . The results of the analysis of rings of both types are given below.

Type I: Rings separated by Clear Spaces

TABLE I

PbI₂ rings in agar-agar.

Distribution of Pb as PbSO_4 in rings and clear spaces.

No.	Ring or space.	Wt. of ring or space.	Wt. of PbSO_4 .	Wt. per g.	Relative amt. per g. of gel.
1	Ring	0.3116 g.	0.0074 g.	0.02268	4.08
2	Ring	0.1112	0.0044	0.03957	7.00
3	Ring	0.1286	0.0062	0.04820	8.70
4	Clear space	0.2520	0.0014	0.00555	1.00
5	Clear space	0.1444	0.0008	0.00554	1.00

TABLE II

Pb(IO₃)₂ rings in gelatin.

Distribution of Pb as PbSO_4 in rings and clear spaces.

No.	Ring or space.	Wt. of ring or space.	Wt. of PbSO_4 .	Wt. per g.	Relative amt. per g. of gel.
1	Ring	0.1314 g.	0.0022 g.	0.01670	2.40
2	Ring	0.0942	0.0030	0.0311	4.50
3	Ring	0.0976	0.0040	0.0410	5.90
4	Clear space	0.2599	0.0018	0.0069	1.00
5	Clear space	0.2778	0.0020	0.0071	1.03

TABLE III

Copper arsenate rings in gelatin.

Distribution of copper in rings and clear spaces estimated volumetrically.

No.	Ring or space.	Wt. of ring or space.	Vol. of sodium thiosulphate.	Vol. of sodium thiosulphate per g. of gel.	Relative amt. per g. of gel.
1	Ring	0.5840 g.	5.25 c.c.	8.99 c.c.	89.9
2	Ring	0.4422	7.69	7.69	76.9
3	Ring	0.3448	2.40	6.95	69.5
4	Clear space	0.9914	0.10	0.10	1.1
5	Clear space	1.6196	0.15	0.09	1.0

TABLE IV

Zinc sulphite rings in gelatin.

Distribution of Zn as zinc ammonium phosphate.

No.	Ring or space.	Wt. of ring or space.	Wt. of zinc ammonium phosphate.	Wt. of zinc amm. phos. per g. of gel.	Relative amt. per g. of gel.
1	Ring	0.2250 g.	0.0136 g.	0.06043 g.	6.504
2	Ring	0.2294	0.0184	0.08221	8.636
3	Clear space	0.3982	0.0232	0.00962	1.000

Type II: Continuous Precipitate showing Banded Structures.

TABLE V

Silver chloride bands in gelatin.

Distribution of Ag as silver chloride in bands.

No.	Band.	Wt. of band.	Wt. of AgCl.	Wt. of AgCl per g. of gel.	Relative amt. per g. of gel.
1	Grey	0.3430 g.	0.0024 g.	0.0070 g.	1.2
2	Black	0.3544	0.0024	0.0067	1.1
3	Grey	0.3508	0.0023	0.0068	1.15
4	Black	0.3834	0.0022	0.0059	1.00

TABLE VI

Silver iodide bands in agar-agar.

Distribution of Ag as silver iodide in bands.

No.	Band.	Wt. of band.	Wt. of AgI	Wt. of AgI per g. of gel.	Relative amt. per g. of gel.
1	Yellowish white	0.3264 g.	0.0014 g.	0.0046 g.	1.00
2	Grey	0.3128	0.0016	0.0051	1.10
3	Yellowish white	0.3248	0.0015	0.0047	1.08
4	Grey	0.3532	0.0018	0.0050	1.08

DISCUSSION

As already pointed out, Dhar and Chatterji (*loc. cit.*) have given two classes of periodic structures, in one class, a layer of precipitate is followed by a clear zone and in other class, a coagulated sol is followed by a zone of peptised sol. They are of the opinion that in the first class are the substances capable of adsorbing their own sol, while in the second class are the substances which do not adsorb their own sol. Hence, it may be argued that the quantity of the sparingly soluble salt per gram of the gel in both bands of second type of structures will almost be the same, whereas in the first class of rings, the distribution will be uneven. From the results obtained in case of rings of PbI_2 , $Pb(IO_3)_2$, $Cu_3(AsO_4)_2$ and $ZnSO_4$, which belong to the rings of the first type, the amount of the sparingly soluble precipitate per gram of gel in rings vary widely from those in the clear spaces; while in case of $AgCl$ and AgI structures the quantity of the sparingly soluble precipitate in both bands is almost the same. Thus, the results obtained support the view put forward by Dhar and Chatterji. The above conclusions are supported by experiments on the adsorption of the constituent ions and sol of many sparingly soluble salts by their precipitates.

The detailed results of the adsorption experiments will be published later.